

Evolving Dimensions of Learning: Study of students' attitude towards Online Learning with special reference to Latur city

Dr. Vyankat Dhondiba Dhumal

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Rajarshi Shahu Mahavidyalaya, Latur

Corresponding Author – Dr. Vyankat Dhondiba Dhumal

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18502084

Abstract:

This study investigates higher-education students' attitudes toward e-learning in Latur city by applying the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, which conceptualizes online learning through social, cognitive and teaching presences. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 93 students through a structured questionnaire containing socio-demographic variables and Likert-type items measuring Social Presence, Cognitive Presence, Teaching Presence and Overall Attitude. Descriptive statistics indicated moderate levels of all three presences, with Cognitive Presence reporting the highest mean score. Normality tests (Shapiro–Wilk) revealed that the data were not normally distributed, necessitating the use of non-parametric statistical techniques for hypothesis testing.

Mann–Whitney U and Kruskal–Wallis H tests were employed to examine differences across gender, stream of study, education level and daily hours of online learning. The findings revealed no statistically significant group differences, although a few results approached the conventional significance threshold, suggesting weak trends rather than definitive effects. Item-level responses indicated that while students perceive online learning as stimulating curiosity, they express concerns regarding limited application, problem-solving and higher-order engagement. The study concludes that although e-learning ensures accessibility and initial engagement, its pedagogical effectiveness depends on strengthening instructional design, interactivity and learner support mechanisms.

Keywords: Online Learning, Community of Inquiry Framework, Social Presence, Teaching Presence, Cognitive Presence

Introduction:

The rapid growth of information and communication technologies (ICT) has significantly changed the landscape of education across the world. Traditional classroom learning is increasingly being blended with and, in some cases, replaced by technology-enabled learning environments. E-learning, which refers to the use of electronic media, digital platforms and internet-based technologies for teaching and learning, has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing access to education. Online learning platforms such as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), video-based lectures and virtual

classrooms have made education more inclusive by reducing geographical and institutional boundaries.

In the Indian context, initiatives such as Digital India, SWAYAM, DIKSHA, and the National Education Policy – 2020 have further strengthened the role of e-learning by promoting digital integration in education. The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated the rapid adoption of online learning across schools, colleges and universities, compelling students to shift from traditional face-to-face instruction to fully online or blended modes of learning. This sudden transition highlighted both the opportunities and

challenges of e-learning, including issues related to internet access, digital literacy, motivation, engagement and learning effectiveness.

While technological infrastructure for e-learning continues to expand, the effectiveness of such learning environments largely depends on students' attitudes and learning experiences within them. In this context, the Community of Inquiry framework provides a useful lens to understand online learning as a combination of social presence, teaching presence and cognitive presence that together shape meaningful learning experiences. Students' attitudes are influenced not only by access to technology but also by the extent to which they feel socially connected, cognitively engaged and adequately supported by instructors. Therefore, examining students' perceptions through the CoI framework is essential for educators, institutions and policymakers to design learner-centred and pedagogically effective digital education strategies.

Objectives of the Study:

The primary aim of this study is to understand the attitude of students towards e-learning. In the course to meet its primary objectives, following objectives are formulated.

1. To examine the levels of Social Presence, Teaching Presence, Cognitive Presence, and Overall Attitude towards online learning among higher education students.
2. To analyse whether students' perceptions of online learning differ across gender, stream of education, and level of education.
3. To examine whether students' perceptions of online learning differ based on daily hours of online learning.
4. To test the applicability of the Community of Inquiry framework in explaining students' online learning experiences.

Review of Literature:

1. **Nasrin & Biswas (2025)** explored senior secondary students' attitudes toward e-learning in Uttar Pradesh. Results indicate that students generally hold low levels of positive attitude toward e-learning modalities. The researchers used a standardized attitude scale and found no gender differences in attitude scores. They also reported significant correlations between e-learning factors, suggesting that students perceive certain components of online learning more favourably than others, though overall acceptance remains limited.¹
2. **Verma & Nigam (2024)** investigated critical success factors affecting positive attitudes toward e-learning among Indian university students. Using data from 221 respondents, their study found that university support significantly enhances student attitudes, while technological issues negatively influence perceptions. Interestingly, instructor support showed an insignificant effect. The authors conclude that addressing infrastructure challenges and enhancing institutional support are essential for fostering favourable attitudes toward online learning in Indian higher education contexts.²
3. **Saini & Yadav (2023)** examined the influence of students' attitudes toward e-learning on academic achievement in Indian higher education. Through a descriptive design involving 600 undergraduates, the study found that positive attitudes, perceived ease of use, and supportive infrastructure correlate with better academic outcomes. The authors emphasize the need for quality digital content and institutional facilitation to strengthen the link between favourable attitudes and student success in e-learning environments.³

4. **Kayoom (2023)**. Kayoom's mixed-method research explored school children's lived experiences with online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in India. Findings highlight that while e-learning enabled continuity of education, many students faced technology barriers, lack of engagement, and limited interaction. The study emphasized the importance of understanding students' lived perceptions and recommended strategies to address emotional, social, and technical challenges to improve attitudes toward online instruction.⁴
5. **Pandey, Bhelkar & Narlawar (2023)** assessed medical students' knowledge, attitudes and practices toward e-learning. Results showed high levels of positive attitude and good knowledge, with most students using online tools for study continuity. However, many students believed e-learning cannot fully replace practical components of medical education. The authors suggest blended and structured e-learning support to maintain favourable attitudes and learning quality.⁵
6. **Alasmari (2022)** examined how the education system responded to multiple crises through the introduction of e-learning. The study found that e-learning played a transformative role in shifting the attitudes of both teachers and students from neutral to positive. Stakeholders began recognizing the advantages of acquiring new skills and adapting to technology-based instruction. The research highlights that blended learning is likely to dominate the future of education, as it integrates the benefits of both traditional and digital learning. E-learning was found to enhance understanding, engagement, and strategic planning in education.⁶
7. **Giri (2022)** focused on the concept of e-readiness and its role in capacity building and digital transformation. The study emphasized that e-readiness enables institutions and governments to assess preparedness for digital adoption, including in education. Findings indicated that educators used e-readiness frameworks to improve instructional delivery, identify areas of improvement, and enhance engagement and quality. Participants showed favourable attitudes toward digital environments, and the study concluded that e-readiness is a crucial tool for improving performance, monitoring progress, and ensuring effective implementation of e-learning systems.⁷
8. **Khan et al. (2021)** assessed university students' perceptions during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings revealed that majority of students held positive perceptions toward e-learning flexibility, ease of access, and communication potential. Students valued learning at their own pace, though some remained neutral on usability and effectiveness. The study highlights that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly shape favourable attitudes toward e-learning adoption.⁸
9. **Garrison et al. (2000)** introduced the Community of Inquiry framework as a conceptual model to explain how meaningful learning occurs in online environments through the interaction of cognitive, social, and teaching presences. This study systematically elaborates each component and situates the framework within constructivist learning theory. It highlights the role of structured facilitation and collaborative discourse in promoting deep learning. The paper also critically acknowledges contextual and methodological limitations, thereby providing a balanced and theoretically grounded contribution to the literature on online and blended learning.⁹

Research Hypotheses:

The present study seeks to examine whether there is any difference in students' attitudes towards different modes of learning, particularly online and offline learning. Since attitude plays a crucial role in determining students' engagement, satisfaction and effectiveness of learning, it becomes important to analyse whether students respond similarly to both modes or whether one mode is perceived more favourably than the other. On this basis, the following hypotheses are formulated:

- H_0 (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in students' perceptions of online learning across gender, stream of education, level of education, and daily hours of online learning.
- H_1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in students' perceptions of online learning across gender, stream of education, level of education, and daily hours of online learning.

Research Methodology:

The present study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional research design to investigate students' attitude of online learning within the framework of the Community of Inquiry model. Data were collected from 93 students enrolled in higher education institutions using a structured questionnaire consisting of two sections: socio-demographic information and perception-based items. The dependent variables included Social Presence, Teaching Presence, Cognitive Presence and Overall Attitude, all measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The independent variables

comprised gender, stream of education, level of education, and daily hours of online learning. The questionnaire was designed based on established CoI constructs, and internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha.

Descriptive statistics were computed for all variables, and the assumption of normality was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test, which indicated that the data were not normally distributed. Accordingly, non-parametric statistical techniques were employed for hypothesis testing. The Mann–Whitney U test was applied for comparisons involving two independent groups, while the Kruskal–Wallis H test was used for comparisons across more than two groups. All analyses were performed using *Jamovi* statistical software with a significance level of 0.05, and ethical standards such as informed consent, voluntary participation, and confidentiality of responses were strictly maintained.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The collected data were analysed to examine students' perceptions of online learning using the Community of Inquiry framework. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis) summarized response patterns, while the Shapiro–Wilk test indicated non-normality. Therefore, non-parametric tests were used: the Mann–Whitney U test for two-group comparisons (e.g., gender, education level) and the Kruskal–Wallis H test for variables with more than two groups (e.g., stream, daily online hours). Analyses in *Jamovi* ($\alpha = 0.05$) provided insights into social, cognitive, and teaching presences and overall attitudes.

Sample Statistics:

Table No. 1: Descriptive Statistics of Social, Cognitive, and Teaching Presence

	Social Presence	Cognitive Presence	Teaching Presence
N	93	93	93
Mean	3.05	3.37	3.12
Median	3.17	3.33	3.17
Standard deviation	0.655	0.462	0.499
Skewness	-0.220	-0.962	0.138
Std. error skewness	0.250	0.250	0.250
Kurtosis	-0.791	0.962	0.192
Std. error kurtosis	0.495	0.495	0.495
Shapiro-Wilk W	0.972	0.898	0.950
Shapiro-Wilk p	0.040	<.001	0.001

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

The descriptive statistics indicate that students' perceptions of online learning were moderate across Social, Cognitive, and Teaching Presences. Cognitive Presence had the highest mean score (3.37), suggesting that students felt most engaged in understanding, analysing, and applying knowledge during online learning. Teaching Presence (3.12) and Social Presence (3.05) were slightly lower, indicating that instructional guidance and social interactions were perceived as moderately effective. Skewness values show a slight negative skew for Social and Cognitive Presences, implying more students rated these aspects above average, while Teaching Presence was nearly symmetrical.

Shapiro–Wilk tests revealed that all three presences significantly deviated from normality ($p < 0.05$), supporting the use of non-parametric analyses for further comparisons. Kurtosis values indicate relatively normal distributions, though Cognitive Presence showed slight leptokurtic. Overall, these findings suggest that while students are cognitively engaged in online learning, there is room to strengthen teaching and social interactions to enhance the overall online learning experience.

Overview of Students' Attitude towards Social Presence:

FIG NO. 1: STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS SOCIAL PRESENCE IN ONLINE LEARNING

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

The above chart indicates that a majority of the 93 respondents reported positive perceptions of social presence in the online learning environment. For the item related to expressing opinions freely, approximately 47% of respondents selected "Agree" and 12% selected "Strongly Agree." For the item on feeling socially connected, approximately 54% selected "Agree" and 3% selected "Strongly Agree." In both cases, the combined agreement categories exceed 50%, while the combined disagreement categories remain below 20%, indicating a generally positive response pattern for these indicators.

For the items reflecting distraction and isolation, the response pattern differs. Approximately 31% of respondents selected "Neutral" for the statement on distraction, while

approximately 29% selected “Disagree” and 14% selected “Strongly Disagree” for the statement on feeling isolated. For the item on peer interaction, approximately 29% selected “Disagree” and 30% selected “Strongly Disagree,” indicating that about 59% did not view peer interaction as adding significant value. These distributions indicate variation across different dimensions of social presence.

Overview of Students’ Attitude towards Teaching Presence:

FIG NO. 2: STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PRESENCE IN ONLINE LEARNING

(Source: Author’s own survey data.)

Among the three positively framed Teaching Presence items (facilitation of discussions, clarity of explanations, and appropriateness of teaching methods), the combined proportion of “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” responses ranged from 25% to 49%. The mean proportion of combined agreement across these three items was 41%. The mean proportion of neutral responses across these items was 25%, and the mean proportion of combined disagreement (“Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree”) was 24%. At the individual item level, combined agreement was 25% for facilitation of discussions, 49% for clarity of explanations, and 48% for appropriateness of teaching methods. The remaining responses for these items were distributed between neutral and disagreement categories, with neutral responses ranging from

3% to 52% and combined disagreement ranging from 22% to 39%.

For the three negatively framed Teaching Presence items (little or no feedback, instructor not available for clarification, and explanations are confusing), the combined proportion of “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” responses ranged from 20% to 39%, with a mean of 31%. Neutral responses for these items ranged from 31% to 55%, while combined disagreement ranged from 18% to 27%. At the item level, combined agreement was 39% for the item on little or no feedback, 34% for the item on lack of instructor availability, and 20% for the item on confusing explanations. The remaining responses were distributed across the neutral and disagreement categories as reported above.

Overview of Students’ Attitude towards Cognitive Presence:

FIG NO. 3: STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS COGNITIVE PRESENCE IN ONLINE LEARNING

(Source: Author’s own survey data.)

The empirical data illustrates a significant disparity between the stimulation of student interest and the attainment of higher-order cognitive engagement within digital environments. While 60% of participants reported that online sessions effectively stimulate their curiosity (28% strongly agreeing and 32% agreeing), this initial interest does not consistently manifest as sustained intellectual involvement. Notably, a combined 70% of respondents expressed agreement with the statement that they

do not feel intellectually engaged during the learning process, with a 51% majority indicating strong agreement. Furthermore, the capacity for the digital medium to foster analytical depth appears limited, as only 25% of the cohort perceived that online learning assisted in critical thinking regarding the subject matter.

Regarding the practical utility of the curriculum, the findings reveal a profound deficit in the application-based outcomes of online instruction. A substantial 84% of students indicated significant difficulty in relating theoretical content to real-world scenarios, a figure matched by an equal 84% who agreed that the online process fails to facilitate the development of essential problem-solving skills. This conceptual disconnect is further evidenced by the low percentage of students (32%) who felt able to bridge new information with prior knowledge effectively.

Testing of Hypotheses:

The present study tested whether students' attitudes toward online learning differ across four grouping variables: gender, stream of study, education level (UG vs PG) and daily hours spent in online learning. The null hypothesis (H_0) stated that there are no significant differences in perceptions of online learning across these groups; the alternative (H_1) posited the existence of such differences. Given that the dependent measures (social, cognitive, teaching presences and an overall attitude score) derive from Likert-type items and some group sizes differ, non-parametric procedures were employed: Mann–Whitney U tests for two-group comparisons (gender, education level) and Kruskal–Wallis H tests for multi-group comparisons (stream, daily hours). An alpha of 0.05 was adopted. The following subsections present the test outcomes and their interpretation for each grouping variable, noting effect

implications, any near-threshold results, and recommendations for further inquiry where appropriate.

Testing for differences in student's attitude across gender:

Table No. 2: Mann–Whitney U Test Results by Gender

		Statistic	p
Social Presence	Mann-Whitney U	1048	0.802
Cognitive Presence	Mann-Whitney U	1066	0.910
Teaching Presence	Mann-Whitney U	1012	0.592
Overall Attitude	Mann-Whitney U	1068	0.919

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

Comparisons between female and male students used U tests for each presence and the overall attitude. The test statistics and p-values were: Social Presence $U = 1048$, $p = 0.802$; Cognitive Presence $U = 1066$, $p = 0.910$; Teaching Presence $U = 1012$, $p = 0.592$; Overall Attitude $U = 1068$, $p = 0.919$. All p-values substantially exceed the 0.05 threshold, so we fail to reject H_0 for every outcome. In practical terms, the data provide no evidence of systematic differences in how male and female respondents perceive social, cognitive or teaching aspects of online learning, nor in their overall attitude. Because non-parametric tests compare rank distributions rather than means, these results suggest similar central tendency and dispersion across genders. Given the consistently high p-values, gender does not appear to be a meaningful discriminator of online-learning attitudes in this sample.

Testing for differences in student's attitude across stream of study:

Table No. 3: Kruskal–Wallis H Test Results by stream of study

	χ^2	df	P
Social Presence	5.6512	2	0.059
Cognitive Presence	3.7222	2	0.155
Teaching Presence	0.0187	2	0.991
Overall Attitude	0.6620	2	0.718

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

H tests examined differences across streams. Results were: Social Presence $\chi^2(2) = 5.6512$, $p = 0.059$; Cognitive Presence $\chi^2(2) = 3.7222$, $p = 0.155$; Teaching Presence $\chi^2(2) = 0.0187$, $p = 0.991$; Overall Attitude $\chi^2(2) = 0.662$, $p = 0.718$. None of the p-values fall below 0.05, so the null hypothesis is retained for all four outcomes. Notably, Social Presence returned a $p = 0.059$, which is marginally above the conventional cutoff and indicates a weak trend that merits attention. A marginal result like this suggests slight rank differences among streams for social presence but not at conventional significance. Further a post hoc analysis revealed that there were no significant differences in social presence perception across three streams of study.

Testing for differences in student's attitude across level of education:

Table No. 4: Mann–Whitney U Test Results by level of education

		Statistic	p
Social Presence	Mann-Whitney U	617	0.063
Cognitive Presence	Mann-Whitney U	791	0.742
Teaching Presence	Mann-Whitney U	662	0.139
Overall Attitude	Mann-Whitney U	684	0.197

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

Education-level comparisons between undergraduate and postgraduate students were tested with U statistics: Social Presence $U = 617$,

$p = 0.063$; Cognitive Presence $U = 791$, $p = 0.742$; Teaching Presence $U = 662$, $p = 0.139$; Overall Attitude $U = 684$, $p = 0.197$. All p-values exceed 0.05, so we do not reject H_0 . The Social Presence result ($p = 0.063$) is close to significance and may indicate a weak difference in ranked responses between UG and PG participants; nevertheless, it again fails conventional significance criteria. However, post hoc analysis revealed that social presence perceptions were not different across undergraduate and postgraduate students. For the cognitive and overall measures, p-values are comfortably non-significant, indicating similar rank distributions across education levels. These findings imply that, within this sample, being an undergraduate or postgraduate student is not associated with substantially different perceptions of online learning.

Testing for differences in student's attitude across hours of online learning:

Table No. 5: Kruskal–Wallis H Test Results by hours of online learning

	χ^2	df	p
Social Presence	3.08	3	0.379
Cognitive Presence	5.00	3	0.171
Teaching Presence	6.65	3	0.084
Overall Attitude	1.43	3	0.698

(Source: Author's own survey data.)

The effect of reported daily hours of online learning was assessed with H tests across four hour-categories. Test outcomes were: Social Presence $\chi^2(3) = 3.08$, $p = 0.379$; Cognitive Presence $\chi^2(3) = 5.00$, $p = 0.171$; Teaching Presence $\chi^2(3) = 6.65$, $p = 0.084$; Overall Attitude $\chi^2(3) = 1.43$, $p = 0.698$. None of these results reach statistical significance at $\alpha = 0.05$. Teaching Presence returned a $p = 0.084$ — the closest to significance — suggesting a possible but inconclusive pattern whereby differing online

exposure relates to perceived teaching presence. Further post hoc analysis indicated that teaching presence perception does not differ due to hours of online learning exposure. Overall, the lack of significance indicates that, in this dataset, the number of hours students spend daily in online learning does not systematically differentiate their social, cognitive or overall attitudinal responses.

Overall, the findings indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in students' perceptions of online learning across gender, stream of study, education level, and daily hours of online learning. The null hypothesis was therefore retained for all four variables. Although a few results approached the conventional level of significance, particularly for social and teaching presence, these did not reach the threshold required for rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that students' attitudes towards online learning are largely consistent across different demographic and academic groups in the present sample.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the data analysis and hypothesis testing, this section proposes a set of targeted recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of online learning. These recommendations are derived directly from the observed patterns in students' perceptions of social, cognitive and teaching presence, as well as from the identified limitations in interaction, application and instructional support. The aim is to translate empirical insights into practical and pedagogically meaningful actions that can improve the quality of online education and promote deeper student engagement and learning outcomes.

1. Strengthening Teaching Presence through Pedagogical Training: Given the moderate scores on Teaching Presence and the absence of strong group differences, institutions

should prioritize faculty development in online instructional design, facilitation strategies, and feedback mechanisms. Training programs should focus on enhancing clarity of instruction, timely academic support, and structured engagement techniques to improve students perceived instructional quality and learning guidance.

2. Integrating Applied and Higher-Order Learning Activities: The finding that students report curiosity but limited application and problem-solving suggests the need to embed applied learning strategies such as case-based learning, project work, and problem-based tasks into online curricula. These methods would facilitate deeper cognitive engagement and promote the transfer of knowledge to practical contexts.

3. Enhancing Structured Peer Interaction: Moderate Social Presence scores and weak interaction-related outcomes indicate the need for deliberately designed peer engagement mechanisms. Structured discussion forums, collaborative assignments, and peer feedback activities should be systematically incorporated to promote meaningful social interaction and shared knowledge construction.

4. Adopting Blended Instructional Models As attitudes did not significantly differ across demographic or academic groups, a blended learning approach can be implemented as a universal model rather than group-specific interventions. Combining synchronous and asynchronous formats can balance flexibility with real-time engagement, thereby strengthening both social and teaching presence.

5. Implementing Continuous Monitoring and Feedback Systems: Institutions should establish regular evaluation mechanisms to monitor students' perceptions and learning

experiences over time. Periodic feedback collection and learning analytics can help identify emerging issues early and support data-informed instructional improvements aligned with students' evolving needs.

6. Enhancing Students' Digital Learning Skills and Self-Regulation: The moderate levels of cognitive engagement and the reported difficulty in applying knowledge suggest that students may require greater support in developing effective online learning strategies. Institutions should therefore provide structured orientation programs focusing on digital literacy, self-regulated learning, time management, and academic use of online platforms to enable students to engage more productively and independently with online learning environments.

Scope for Further Research:

The present study is limited by its relatively small sample size, cross-sectional design and geographic focus on a single city, which restricts generalizability and causal interpretation. Future research should employ larger, multi-institutional samples across diverse regions to capture contextual variations in infrastructure, digital literacy and institutional readiness. Longitudinal designs would enable researchers to examine how students' perceptions of online learning evolve over time and how attitudes relate to academic performance, retention and skill development.

Further studies should adopt mixed-methods approaches incorporating interviews or focus groups to explore why students report high curiosity but limited application and critical thinking. Experimental designs testing specific pedagogical strategies—such as problem-based learning, collaborative tasks or blended models—would help identify effective interventions.

Comparative studies across disciplines and learning platforms would also enhance understanding of domain-specific challenges and opportunities, contributing to evidence-based improvements in e-learning practice.

Conclusion:

This study examined students' attitudes toward online learning through the lenses of social, cognitive and teaching presence. The results indicate moderate levels of all three presences, with Cognitive Presence being relatively stronger. Inferential analysis revealed no significant differences across gender, stream of study, education level or daily hours of online learning, suggesting that students' perceptions are broadly consistent across demographic and academic groups. However, some results approached statistical significance, indicating possible weak patterns that merit further exploration with larger samples.

The findings reveal a critical paradox: students acknowledge the accessibility and motivational aspects of e-learning, yet report limitations in real-world application, interaction and higher-order learning. This highlights the need to move beyond mere technological provision toward pedagogically rich, interactive and student-centred online environments. Strengthening teaching presence, fostering collaboration and integrating applied learning activities are essential for improving educational outcomes. Overall, the study underscores that the effectiveness of online learning lies not in technology alone but in its thoughtful and evidence-based pedagogical implementation.

References:

1. Nasrin, & Biswas, K. (2025). Attitude of senior secondary school students toward e-learning. *Educational Trend (A Journal of RIE, Ajmer – NCERT)*, 5(2), 161–181.

- <https://ejournals.ncert.gov.in/index.php/ET/article/view/3782>
2. Verma, I., & Nigam, S. (2024). Facilitating positive attitude in students: A study of critical e-learning factors. *Indian Journal of Educational Technology*, 6(I), 79–89. <https://journals.ncert.gov.in/IJET/article/view/404>
 3. Saini, P., & Yadav, A. (2025). The influence of e-learning attitude on academic success: Insights from India. *International Journal of Research in STEM Education*, 7(2), 62–76. <https://doi.org/10.33830/ijrse.v7i2.1822>
 4. Kayoom, H. (2023). A Study on the Attitude towards E-Learning and its Implication on School Children during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Indian Journal of Educational Technology*, 5(I), 78–88. <https://journals.ncert.gov.in/IJET/article/view/403>
 5. Pandey, S., Bhelkar, S., & Narlawar, U. W. (2022). Knowledge, attitudes and practices of medical students towards electronic learning in a tertiary care centre in central India: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 9(12), 4549–4554. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20223212>
 6. Alasmari, A. (2022). The Attitudes of Public-School Teachers towards E-learning in Saudi Arabia. *Arab World English Journal*, 245-257, <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/covid2.16>
 7. Giri, P. (2022). E-readiness and capacity building for e-learning adoption in education systems. *International Journal of Rural Management*, 21(1), 159-166, <https://doi.org/10.47760/ijcsmc.2022.v11i01.023>
 8. Khan, M. A., Vivek, Kamalun Nabi, M., Khojah, M., & Tahir, M. (2021). Students' perception towards e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in India: An empirical study. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010057>
 9. D. Randy Garrison, Terry Anderson, Walter Archer, *Critical Inquiry in a Text-Based Environment: Computer Conferencing in Higher Education, The Internet and Higher Education*, Volume 2, Issues 2–3, 1999, Pages 87-105, ISSN 1096-7516, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516\(00\)00016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516(00)00016-6)
 10. Akyol, Z., & Garrison, D. R. (2011). Understanding cognitive presence in an online and blended community of inquiry: Assessing outcomes and processes for deep approaches to learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 42(2), 233–250. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2009.01029.x>
 11. Annand, D. (2011). Social presence within the community of inquiry framework. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 12(5), 40–56. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v12i5.924>
 12. Fiock, H. S. (2020). Designing a community of inquiry in online courses. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. <https://www.irrodl.org/>
 13. Garrison, D. R., Anderson, T., & Archer, W. (2000). Critical inquiry in a text-based environment: Computer conferencing in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 2(2–3), 87–105. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516\(00\)00016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516(00)00016-6)
 14. Garrison, D. R., Anderson, T., & Archer, W. (2001). Critical thinking, cognitive presence, and computer conferencing in distance education. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923640109527071>
 15. Garrison, D. R., & Anderson, T. (2003). *E-learning in the 21st century: A framework for research and practice*. Routledge Falmer. <https://www.routledge.com/>
 16. Garrison, D. R., & Arbaugh, J. B. (2007). Researching the community of inquiry framework: Review, issues, and future directions. *Internet and Higher Education*, 10(3), 157–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2007.04.001>

17. Arbaugh, J. B., Cleveland-Innes, M., Diaz, S. R., Garrison, D. R., Ice, P., Richardson, J. C., & Swan, K. P. (2008). Developing a community of inquiry instrument: Testing a measure of the Community of Inquiry framework using a multi-institutional sample. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 11(3–4), 133–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2008.06.003>
18. Richardson, J. C., & Swan, K. (2003). Examining social presence in online courses in relation to students perceived learning and satisfaction. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 7(1), 68–88. <https://olj.onlinelearningconsortium.org/index.php/olj/article/view/1865>
19. Shea, P., Li, C. S., & Pickett, A. (2006). A study of teaching presence and student sense of learning community in online and web-enhanced college courses. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 9(3), 175–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2006.06.003>
20. Swan, K., & Shih, L. (2005). On the nature and development of social presence in online course discussions. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 9(3), 115–136. <https://olj.onlinelearningconsortium.org/index.php/olj/article/view/1869>
21. Shea, P., & Bidjerano, T. (2010). Learning presence: Towards a theory of self-efficacy, self-regulation, and the development of learning in online and blended learning environments. *Computers & Education*, 55(4), 1721–1731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.07.017>
22. Kovanović, V., Joksimović, S., Gašević, D., Siemens, G., & Hatala, M. (2017). What public media reveals about learners' community of inquiry experience. *The Internet and Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.01.002>
23. Shea, P. (2010). The community of inquiry framework ten years later. *Internet and Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.10.001>
24. Garrison, D. R. (2024). Evidence-based practices for developing a community of inquiry. In *Handbook of Research in Online Learning* (pp. 276–306). Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004702813_012
25. Adeniji-Neill, D., et al. (2018). Community of Inquiry in online learning environments. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 14, 155–168. <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2018.155.168>
26. Javaid, M., et al. (2015). Community of Inquiry as an instructional approach: Teaching, social and cognitive presence in blended synchronous learning. *Computers & Education*, 81, 191–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.10.015>
27. Li, Y., Meng, N., & Ye, X. (2024). Effects of community of inquiry, learning presence and mentor presence on K-12 online learning outcomes. *Education Sciences*, 12(4), 245. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12040245>
28. Online Learning Consortium. (2021). Roundup on research: Community of inquiry model overview. <https://onlineteaching.umich.edu/articles/round-up-on-research-community-of-inquiry/>
29. Whitley, E., & Ball, J. (2002). Statistics review 6: Nonparametric methods. *Critical Care*, 6(6), 509–513. <https://doi.org/10.1186/cc1820>
30. Pandit, D. N. (2022). *Statistics: A modern approach (includes hypothesis testing and test of significance)*. Hindustan Publishing Corporation
31. Mishra, A. (2020). *Theory of statistical hypothesis testing*. Notion Press
32. Gupta, S. P. (2021). *Statistical methods* (46th ed.). Sultan Chand & Sons.